

HYGROTHERMAL EFFECT ON MODE-II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF A CARBON/POLYPHENYLENE SULFIDE LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

By using a double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen, the hygrothermal effect on Mode II (in-plane shear loading) interlaminar fracture toughness of a carbon/polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) unidirectional laminate was investigated. The critical strain energy release rates, G_{IIc} , of the carbon/PPS laminate during crack propagation under Mode II loading for various temperature/relative humidity conditions were obtained both by linear beam theory and by the area method. It was found that the critical strain energy release rate of the carbon/PPS laminate increases with both moisture content and temperature. Fracture of the carbon/PPS laminate was characterized primarily by microcracking at low temperature/low moisture content and by matrix softening and fiber bridging at high temperature/high moisture content.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites have in the past been utilized mainly for weight savings in secondary structures. Currently, they are being considered for use as primary load bearing structures. To meet the need for improved damage tolerance in composite structures, designers are looking towards tough resin systems to overcome the poor impact and delamination growth resistance of currently used epoxy resins. Elastomer modified epoxies and new thermoplastics are being developed by manufacturers of composite materials. One of the most exciting thermoplastics is polyphenylene sulfide (PPS).

The PPS used as the polymer matrix for high performance composites is a modified polymer [1] in which the polymerization reaction is carried out directly to a high molecular weight. This results in a tough PPS polymer which can be used for injection molding compounds, for random fiber stampable sheets [2], or continuous fiber fabric prepregs [3].

The full potential of the fiber reinforcement can not be realized due to the random fiber orientation and fiber discontinuity in short fiber reinforced composites. The recent development of a new, higher molecular weight version of this polymer, followed by its marriage with long fiber reinforcement in composites, has resulted in an even higher performance family of materials. Successful impregnation of continuous high performance fibers has resulted in the production of continuous fiber prepreg tapes containing carbon, aramid and glass reinforcing fibers.

Interlaminar cracking, sometimes also called delamination, is one of the most frequently encountered types of damage in advanced composite materials. The presence and growth of interlaminar cracks in composite laminates may lead to severe reliability and safety problems, such as the reduction of structural stiffness, exposure of the interior to adverse environment

and disintegration of the material, which may cause the final failure. Thus understanding the basic mechanics of interlaminar cracking is of critical importance in the characterization of flaw criticality and assessment of structural integrity of advanced composite materials and structures. The ability to resist defect propagation is characterized by the material's fracture toughness. The interlaminar fracture toughness of a composite material is often characterized by the critical strain energy release rate, G_C . The stresses at a delamination crack tip can be decomposed into three components. The critical strain energy release rates are classified as G_{IC} , G_{IIC} and G_{IIIC} accordingly. Delamination growth in laminated fiber reinforced composite materials consists of three stages, namely, initiation, slow growth and ply separation.

The delamination fracture toughness of a graphite/epoxy composite under various Mode I/Mode II load ratios was investigated experimentally [4]. The critical strain energy release rate was determined by using a double cantilever beam specimen, linear elastic fracture mechanics, linear beam theory, and analysis of an asymmetric loading scheme by superposition of solutions for pure opening and pure bending components. Delamination cracking under Mode II loads traversed entire laminae resulting in considerable fiber breakage and pullout, which accounts for the dramatic increase in initial energy release rate as compared to pure Mode I delamination. The effect of matrix toughness on delamination was studied [5]. It was indicated that the benefits of improved matrix toughness on the composite properties were less under Mode II loading than under Mode I and were reduced further still, or eliminated entirely under Mode II fatigue conditions. The influence of the resin on the mixed-mode fracture was studied [6]. It was shown that high Mode I toughness requires resin dilatation (volume increase). Dilatation is low in unmodified epoxies at room temperature/dry conditions; dilatation is higher in plasticized epoxies, heated epoxies, and in modified epoxies. Loading rate effects on interlaminar fracture toughness were investigated [7 & 8] for graphite/epoxy and graphite/PEEK composites. The results indicated that the interlaminar fracture toughness decreases with increasing loading rate. This decrease was up to 65 percent over the five decades of loading rate employed. A study of moisture content, temperature and ply orientation effects on graphite/epoxy laminates was undertaken in [9]. It was shown that crack extension in Mode I resulted in enhanced fracture energies due primarily to fiber bridging. The maximum or stabilized energy was strongly dependent upon temperature, moisture content and ply orientation in the delamination plane. Mechanisms of interlaminar fracture in graphite/epoxy systems were investigated [10, 11 & 12]. It was found that interlaminar fracture mechanisms in thermoplastic matrix composites are associated with extensive matrix deformation around the crack tip. A stretching and cavitation process proceeds in the crack tip plastic zone. The extent of matrix deformation depends on the velocity of crack propagation.

Most of the work reported to date on delamination fracture of composites has been concerned with the opening mode tensile crack extension in ambient temperature/dry environments. However, predictions based on measurements at a single set of conditions can lead to dangerous overestimate or underestimate of the mechanical properties. To the authors' knowledge, no investigations have been made to study the significance of moisture and temperature on the Mode II interlaminar fracture behavior. In this paper, a double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen was used to evaluate Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the carbon/PPS laminate under a variety of temperature/relative humidity conditions.

2. DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL

The carbon/PPS prepreg (AC40-66) used in the present investigation was supplied from Phillips Petroleum Company. Hercules AS-4 carbon fiber rovings containing 12000 filament counts were used to make a prepreg tape 4 inch (100mm) wide and 0.008 inch (0.2mm) thick. The prepreg contains 66% by weight carbon fibers. The diameter of the carbon fiber is 8 μm .

The as-received PPS materials were subjected to differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) tests to determine their glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_m) and latent heat of melting. The determination of T_g was carried out according to ASTM D3418 on a Dupont 910 differential scanning calorimeter at a heating rate of 20°C/minute in a nitrogen atmosphere with the temperature ranging from 30 to 330°C for the first run and from 30 to 180°C for the second run.

The first run of AC40-66 prepreg was performed in order to erase any previous thermal history. Each sample was cooled with liquid nitrogen after the first run. T_g was determined to be 90.8°C. The determination of melting temperature and latent heat of melting of AC40-66 prepreg was done according to ASTM D3418 and D3417 at a heating rate of 10°C/minute in a nitrogen atmosphere. The onset of melting temperature on the flow rate-temperature curve was observed by extrapolation to be 254.0°C. The final melting temperature was determined to be 270.1°C and the latent heat of melting was determined to be 26.8 J/g. The DSC results of the as-received carbon/PPS prepreg are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1 DSC RESULTS OF AC40-66 PREPREG (AS-RECEIVED)

	#1	Specimen #2	#3
Glass transition temperature (°C)	91.0	90.8	---
Onset melting point (°C)	253.0	254.0	252.9
Final melting point (°C)	269.8	270.1	270.8
Latent heat of melting (J/g)	26.1	26.8	27.7

Above their melting temperature (T_m), crystallizable resins are in an amorphous state. Below their glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallization occurs at a very slow rate. Most crystalline polymers will remain nearly completely amorphous when quenched in water from the melt. One way for achieving crystallinity in polymers is to anneal the amorphous film at temperatures between T_g and T_m . According to Mascia [13], as crystallization proceeds the spherulites will eventually touch each other and, as a result, the uncrystallized polymer chains at the boundaries will find it increasingly more difficult to diffuse to the surface of existing crystals or to nucleate into new crystallites. If after crystallization the polymer is heated to temperatures just below the true melting point, some partial melting of the least perfect crystals takes place. The stable crystals, however, will continue to grow into thicker lamellae and a higher level of crystallinity is developed.

In order to gain the maximum crystallinity in the PPS samples, proper molding and annealing of the prepreps are necessary. The extent and type of crystallinity depend primarily on the molding conditions. To assist the molders of carbon/PPS prepreg, a study was designed to determine the optimum molding conditions [14]. The following molding procedure is based on this study.

Composite laminate of 152mm by 150mm was fabricated by the following steps. First, the as-received prepreg (100mm in width) was cut into sizes of 152mm x 100mm and 152mm x 50mm, respectively. Second, the 100mm wide prepreg was tacked to a 50mm wide prepreg by using a hot soldering iron. It was found [10] that thicker laminates are better suited for testing interlaminar fracture toughness of thermoplastic matrix composites. In the present investigation, 24 piles of prepreg were stacked unidirectionally and the corners tacked to give a prepreg laminate. A teflon tape of 0.0508mm (0.002 inch) thick, 35mm wide and 152mm (6 inch) long, was placed between the central laminae for the purpose of crack initiation. The limit temperature of the teflon tape is 400°C for continuous exposure and 427°C for 30 minutes, respectively. The teflon tape was found to be in intact condition (non-melting) in the molded laminates for the present molding temperature. The stacked prepreps were put into a steel mold of 6 x 6 inch. The mold was then placed between two platens of a preheated platen press at 316°C. Heat is transferred from the two platens to the mold and to the material by conduction.

A thermocouple was put near the internal wall of the mold, and another one was put between the central plies of the laminate to monitor the temperatures of the molding. As indicated in Figure 1, the maximum temperature difference of the laminate and the internal wall of the mold

was about 3 to 5°C, which shows a fairly good temperature distribution over the material. Contact pressure of 5 psi (0.034 MPa) was applied for 16 minutes until the temperature of the laminate reached 310°C followed by a pressure of 1.0 MPa for additional 3 minutes. During this 3-minute period, the temperature reached about 316°C. The hot laminate was then cooled under the pressure of 1.0 MPa to 38°C in 18 minutes by cooling the two platens with a mixture of water and air (two-phase flow). The cooling rate can be controlled by adjusting the flow rates of the cooling water and air. It was, however, held constant in the present investigation.

The molded laminate was trimmed and cut into specimens of 152mm long, 25mm wide (as B in the Nomenclature), and 3.84mm thick (as 2D). The initial starter crack length is about 35mm (as a_0). Annealing was accomplished by subjecting the laminate to a temperature of 200°C, which is between T_g and T_m as listed in Table 1, for a period of 2 hours in an environmental chamber. This gives small crystallites for the PPS morphology. The matrix is fully crystallized. The differential scanning calorimetry trace of annealed sample shows only a small change at T_g , T_m and latent heat of melting and the absence of any crystallization exotherm as indicated in Figure 2. The DSC results in the annealed samples are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2 DSC RESULTS OF AC40-66 LAMINATE (ANNEALED)

	Virgin	87°C	127°C
Glass transition temperature (°C)	94.0	90.5	87.0
Inflexion point (°C)	106.5	102.4	98.2
Onset melting point (°C)	255.8	256.2	253.1
Final melting point (°C)	270.8	270.9	271.3
Latent heat of melting (J/g)	28.6	33.0	47.5

3. DATA REDUCTION

A specially designed test fixture for the study of Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness is shown in Figure 3. As the crack grows between the central plies of the specimen, energy is released since the cracked section is more compliant than the uncracked.

The small displacement solution for the end notched double cantilever beam may be deduced from the compliance [5]

$$C = \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{1}{2EBD^3} (3a^3 + L^3) \quad (1)$$

The strain energy release rate can be obtained from

$$G_{II} = \frac{P^2}{2} \frac{\partial C}{\partial A} = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{9}{4} \frac{P^2 a^2}{EB^2 D^3} \quad (2)$$

The critical strain energy release rate, G_{IIC} , can then be obtained from Equation (2) by replacing P with P_c , the critical load at the onset of the crack propagation.

The above is the well known linear beam theory. According to [4], nonlinear beam theory gives significantly different predictions from linear beam theory when large deflections and rotations occur. However, the load-displacement curves of these laminates were found to be

basically linear as indicated in Figures 5(a-h). Therefore, the linear beam theory was employed in the present investigation to determine the Mode II critical strain energy release rate, G_{IIc} , of the carbon/PPS laminates. Furthermore the values of G_{IIc} were also compared to the average values by the area method to be explained below to validate the application of the linear beam theory in the present investigation.

The area methods, whereby the area under a load-displacement record for loading, crack advance from a_1 to a_2 , and unloading is determined by integrating and assumed to be equal to the work required to increase the crack area by $B(a_2 - a_1)$. This method assumes that all the work represented by the area bounded by the load, crack advance, unload-displacement curve goes into crack advance. Any far field energy dissipation would erroneously be lumped into the energy absorbed per unit area of crack extension relationship [12].

4. STABILITY ANALYSIS OF CRACK GROWTH IN DCB SPECIMEN

The stability of crack growth may be judged from the sign of dG_{II}/da . For fixed grip condition (displacement control), dG_{II}/da can be obtained after substitution of $P = d/C$ into Equation (2) and differentiation,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dG_{II}}{da} &= \frac{\delta^2}{2B} \frac{d^2 \left(\frac{1}{C}\right)}{da^2} \\ &= \frac{\delta^2}{2B} \left[\frac{1}{C^2} \frac{D^2 C}{da^2} - \frac{2}{C^3} \left(\frac{dC}{da}\right)^2 \right] \\ &= \frac{9a\delta^2}{2C^2EB^2D^3} \left(1 - \frac{9a^3}{2CEBD^3}\right) \\ &= \frac{9a\delta^2}{2C^2EB^2D^3} \left(1 - \frac{9a^3}{3a^3 + L^3}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For stable crack growth dG_{II}/da has to be less than or equal to zero. Equation (3) gives

$$a/L \geq 1/\sqrt[3]{6} \approx 0.55 \quad (4)$$

In comparison to the case of the End Notched Flexure (ENF) specimen [15] where $a/L \geq 1/\sqrt[3]{3} \approx 0.69$ in order for the crack growth to be stable, the present DCB specimen reaches stable crack growth in a shorter distance.

5. SPECIMEN TESTING

Specimens for interlaminar fracture test were cut from the molded laminates with a water-cooled diamond blade cutoff saw. The edge of the specimen was polished and painted white for better tracking of the crack propagation during the test. Twelve specimens of the same geometry were put in an environmental chamber for each of the four hygrothermal conditions: 87°C/84%, 87°C/95%, 127°C/84% and 127°C/95%. The behavior of moisture absorption of the laminate was studied by weighing the last three specimens at regular time. Three specimens were taken out of the environmental chamber at certain time interval, weighed and tested on an MTS machine. The cross head speed of the MTS machine was set at 3mm/minute in displacement control. Mode II interlaminar fracture tests were performed by loading the cracked end of the specimen. Some flat bearings were embedded in the uncracked end of the specimen to allow the horizontal translation while restricting vertical displacement.

In order to have the crack initiation, the span, L , of the specimen was set about 37mm to have a larger shear stress at crack tip. After the crack initiated, the span of the specimen was

changed to about 85mm. This way one can observe the crack propagation through most of the specimen. The crack length after crack initiation, a_i , was in the range of 28mm to 38mm. From Equation (4), stable crack growth is expected when the crack propagates more than half of the span. This occurred usually after the first loading in the present study. The load-displacement curve for each of the specimens was recorded and the crack length was measured with a digital caliper. During the test, a video camera along with a long distance microscope was used to record and monitor the initiation and propagation of the crack.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The average moisture content of the carbon/PPS laminate was obtained by weighing the last three specimens for each of the four hygrothermal conditions. Moisture content versus square root of time is shown in Figure 4. It is indicated that moisture content increases with time gradually. The higher the relative humidity is in the environmental chamber, the higher the moisture content of the carbon/PPS laminate will be. For a fixed relative humidity, the higher the temperature is in the environmental chamber, the lower the moisture content will be. All samples exposed to the four hot-moist conditions did not show moisture saturation after about 320 hours. The maximum percent moisture uptake for the four temperature/relative humidity conditions are summarized in Table 3.

TABLE 3 MAXIMUM PERCENT MOISTURE UPTAKE OF AC40-66 LAMINATE ANNEALED

Condition	Time (hours)	Maximum percent moisture uptake (%)
87°C/84%	320	0.17
127°C/84%	310	0.08
87°C/95%	320	0.78
127°C/95%	310	0.56

In summary, the laminate absorbs more moisture at low temperature/high relative humidity condition than at high temperature/low relative humidity condition.

The load-displacement curves, Figures 5(a-h), were recorded to identify the various types of crack growth. According to [11], there are three basic types of fracture behavior in the interlaminar fracture of thermoplastics. They are characterized as type I-ductile stable, type II-brittle unstable and type III-brittle stable. All these three types of crack growth were observed in the present investigation.

For the virgin specimen test, shown in Figure 5(a), only brittle stable crack growth was observed. This gives the lowest G_{IIC} values among all the samples. Note that the crack length after crack initiation, a_i , was 38mm. The ratio, $a_i/L = 38/85 = 0.45$.

For the 87°C/84% condition, shown in Figures 5(b-d), the crack growth basically exhibited brittle stable behavior. However, there was one case of brittle unstable behavior, the first loading of the sample at MC = 0.02% shown in Figure 5(c), where the ratio of a_i/L was only 0.30. There was also one case of ductile stable response, the third loading of the sample at MC = 0.13% shown in Figure 5(d).

For the 127°C/95% condition, shown in Figures 5(e-h), type I (ductile stable crack growth) became more obvious, especially at the third loading, shown in Figures 5(g-h), where the moisture contents were higher.

It was also indicated that the critical load and the displacement became larger with the increases of the moisture content and temperature. According to [6], both moisture and heat increase the

ability of polymers to dilate. Moisture may infuse into the polymers, separating the polymer molecules, thus reducing their secondary bond attraction, thereby making it easier for the molecules to move past the critical strain levels. This process is a form of plasticization. Heat creates a similar effect. The higher temperature, especially approaching the glass transition temperature (T_g), causes the materials to expand, thus creating more free volume.

It is concluded from the above observation that the crack growth is becoming stabler as the ratio of the crack length to the span is becoming larger than about 0.55 as predicted in Equation (4), and that the PPS matrix is brittle at low temperature and low moisture content. However, when the moisture content and temperature are high, the matrix exhibits plastic deformation because high moisture content and high temperature soften the PPS matrix and cause fiber bridging. This will be shown in the fractography study section.

The critical strain energy release rate, G_{IIC} , of the virgin specimen was found to be $524 \pm 8 \text{ J/m}^2$ (mean \pm standard deviation) by DCB and $372 \pm 5 \text{ J/m}^2$ by the area method. Compared to the graphite/epoxy system, where the mean value of G_{IIC} was about 160 J/m^2 , and to the graphite/PEEK (polyetheretherketone) system, where the value of G_{IIC} was about 1765 ± 235 (mean \pm standard deviation) [6], carbon/PPS laminate rates between these two thermoplastics.

The values of G_{IIC} by DCB and the average values of G_{IIC} by the area method at different moisture levels are plotted in Figures 6(a-b). As can be seen from Figures 6(a-b), the critical strain energy release rate of carbon/PPS laminate during crack propagation under Mode II loading increases with an increase of moisture content. At a lower relative humidity of 84% and a temperature of 87°C , the critical strain energy release rate, G_{IIC} , increases with an increase of moisture content, from about 551 J/m^2 to 594 J/m^2 (an increase of 8%). At $127^\circ\text{C}/84\%$, G_{IIC} increases with an increase of moisture content, from about 571 J/m^2 to 603 J/m^2 (5.5%). At a higher relative humidity of 95% and a temperature of 87°C , G_{IIC} also increases with an increase of moisture content, from about 563 J/m^2 to 596 J/m^2 (5.9%). At $127^\circ\text{C}/95\%$, G_{IIC} increases from about 577 J/m^2 to 615 J/m^2 (6.7%). It is also indicated that for a fixed moisture content, G_{IIC} increases with an increase of temperature, and that G_{IIC} increases more with temperature at higher moisture contents.

It is indicated from Figures 6(a-b) that the average G_{IIC} values obtained by the area method have the same trend as those by DCB even though the values by the area method are about 68% to 85% of the values by DCB. The difference range is comparable to that of 60% to 70% by [11] for graphite/epoxy system. The higher toughness of PPS resin may have contributed to the better linear load-displacement response, which in turn contributed to the better results by DCB as compared to the results by the area method.

This increase of the critical strain energy release rate is mainly due to the matrix softening and fiber bridging exhibited in the fractured surfaces by the scanning electron microscope and by examining the side view of the specimen using a regular microscope.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The semicrystalline engineering thermoplastic, PPS, has been shown to be an excellent matrix for high performance fiber reinforced composites. The Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the carbon/PPS laminate for various hygrothermal conditions has been determined. From this investigation, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Compared to the critical strain energy release rate under Mode II loading of graphite/epoxy laminates, which is about 160 J/m^2 [6], the carbon/PPS laminate is tougher;
2. The crack propagates only through the resins by microcracking for virgin specimens and for those specimens exposed to low temperature and with low moisture content. The amount of resin deformation in these "smooth" fracture surfaces is small;

3. As the moisture content and temperature increase, an increase of the interlaminar fracture energy is found. This is due to the change in Mode II failure mechanism from the energy absorbing multiple matrix microcracking of the brittle matrix systems to the constrained plastic deformation of the toughened PPS matrix system.

KEY WORDS: Thermoplastic, Composites, Hygrothermal, Interlaminar, Fracture

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Figure 1. Thermal cycle for the molding of AC40-66 laminates.

Figure 2. DSC test of AC40-66 laminate - first run (annealed).

Figure 3. Mode II interlaminar fracture test fixture.

Figure 4. Moisture content versus square root of time for AC40-66 laminate.

Figure 5. Load versus vertical displacement curves for AC40-66 laminate.

Figure 6. Critical strain energy release rate versus moisture content with temperature as a parameter for AC40-66 laminate.